

Template Language for DSI Databases

Supporting the UN Convention on Biological Diversity COP16 Decision 16/2, Annex, Paragraph 10

from Raposo et al. 2026, *How can biological databases support the new UN mechanism for benefit-sharing from digital sequence information?*

To support the requirements for databases that provide access to Digital Sequence Information (DSI), agreed to by consensus of the Parties to the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD)¹ listed in decision 16/2, an international scientific working group developed the following “template language”. The full paper (listed above) and this document are intended to provide practical guidance for database managers that wish to support implementation of CBD Decision 16/2. Database operators are encouraged to adapt the proposed language to align with their internal policies and applicable legal frameworks. The template language does not create, modify, or replace any legal obligations that may arise from implementation at the national level.

As the CBD’s DSI multilateral mechanism and other international benefit-sharing instruments, such as the Food and Agriculture Organization’s Plant Treaty (ITPGRFA), the World Health Organization’s Pathogen ABS System (WHO PABS), and the new High Seas Treaty (BBNJ Agreement), evolve, this language may need to be revisited and updated to maintain coherence across different policy frameworks.

Because many scientific databases have minimal legal and administrative support, template language can provide database managers with a helpful starting point for developing or updating internal policies that can be subsequently tailored to their specific needs. To implement COP16 Decision 16/2 paragraph 10 of its Annex, Table 1 provides examples of draft language that databases can adapt and supplement with additional information appropriate to their setting. The draft language was developed collaboratively by database managers and science-policy experts to align with the CBD new multilateral mechanism². It provides communication guidance for databases on how to reflect access and benefit-sharing principles in their governance language.

Historically, DSI databases have focused their limited resources on developing and maintaining technical and scientific infrastructure. Because many national and international funders and scientific journals require DSI to be openly published to enable scientific reproducibility and integrity, DSI has long been considered an open and public good that needs to be made freely accessible. Most DSI databases align with community norms, such as the Bermuda Principles³ and Fort Lauderdale Agreement⁴, and are working towards related standards (e.g., FAIR, CARE, TRUST principles) to improve practices. Other relevant policy frameworks influence public DSI sharing such as ‘laws regarding the disclosure and use of information’, ‘personal information protection laws’ in the country of the institution that operates each database, which many databases already comply with, such as the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in Europe. Access to genetic resources (i.e. biological samples) should always be obtained through relevant national laws that regulate access and benefit-sharing.

DSI databases communicate rules and responsibilities to users and submitters through a wide range of governance instruments. These can include, inter alia, terms of use, disclaimers, data submission agreements, privacy statements, data licenses and statements of ethical commitment. The structure and placement of such governance instruments vary widely, from short disclaimers of liability, licenses that cover the entire database, to more lengthy and detailed sections that refer to international agreements, national legislation, or ethics policies. Legal information on DSI database websites is often limited to general information on the database provider and formal disclaimers regarding limited liability for content.

Rohden et al. (2020)⁵ found that most sequence databases operate without formal terms of use, with the International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration (INSDC) databases being a notable exception. **With Decision 16/2, DSI database governance will need to evolve. We strongly encourage DSI databases to proactively support implementation of Decision 16/2 and fair and equitable benefit-sharing.**

¹Convention on Biological Diversity (2024). Decision 16/2 (CBD/COP/DEC/16/2). **Digital sequence information on genetic resources.** *Conference of the Parties to the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD)*, UNEP. <https://www.cbd.int/doc/decisions/cop-16/cop-16-dec-02-en.pdf>.

²Facilitated by the FAR-DSI project: <https://www.gfbio-ev.de/en/projects/fardsi/>

³Maxson Jones, K., Ankeny, R. A., & Cook-Deegan, R. (2018). **The Bermuda Triangle: The Pragmatics, Policies, and Principles for Data Sharing in the History of the Human Genome Project.** *Journal of the history of biology*, 51(4), 693–805. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10739-018-9538-7>

⁴Wellcome Trust (2003). **Sharing Data from Large-scale Biological Research Projects: A System of Tripartite Responsibility.** Available at: <https://www.genome.gov/Pages/Research/WellcomeReport0303.pdf>

⁵Rohden, F., Huang, S., Dröge, G. & Scholz, A. H. (2020) CBD/DSI/AHTEG/2020/1/4: **Combined study on Digital Sequence Information (DSI) in public and private databases and traceability.** Available at: <https://www.cbd.int/doc/c/1f8f/d793/57cb114ca40cb6468f479584/dsi-ahteg-2020-01-04-en.pdf>.

Table 1: Template language for DSI databases to reflect the requirements of the Convention on Biological Diversity’s COP16 Decision 16/2, Annex, paragraph 10.

Decision 16/2 text (Annex paragraph 10)	Applies to	Template language	Suggested “location”
10(a) “Make information on the multilateral mechanism for the fair and equitable sharing of benefits arising from the use of digital sequence information on genetic resources available to those accessing their databases and underline that generating monetary benefits from the use of such information accessed through their databases may require the sharing of those benefits through the multilateral mechanism.”	All users	“The data accessed through this database may be subject to benefit-sharing obligations from the use of Digital Sequence Information (DSI) arising from the UN Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD)’s multilateral mechanism, including monetary contributions to the Cali Fund from commercial users. Further information is available here: https://www.cbd.int/califund/guides/guide%20for%20database.pdf .”	General disclaimer section
10(b) “Inform those submitting data of the requirement to comply with applicable national and international access and benefit-sharing obligations.”	Submitters	“Those submitting data are informed they should comply with all applicable national and international laws and regulations, including those governing access and benefit-sharing. Submitters are responsible for compliance with relevant frameworks in the jurisdictions where they operate.”	Data Submission / Ethics
10(c) “Require the provision of information on the country of origin of the genetic resources from which digital sequence information was derived, where known, as well as, when appropriate, metadata associated with the genetic resources from which digital sequence information was derived, including an indication of the use of traditional knowledge associated with the genetic resources and its origin or source.”	Submitters	“Submitters are required to include, where known, information on where the genetic resources were originally collected (<i>in-situ</i>), also known as geolocation of sampling, from which the sequence data were derived ⁶ .” “Where appropriate, further relevant metadata associated with that genetic resource should also be provided. For example, if traditional knowledge associated with the genetic resource was utilized, the submission should indicate this and include the origin or source of that traditional knowledge.”	Data Submission Metadata Guidelines

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Decision 16/2 text (Annex paragraph 10)	Applies to	Template language	Suggested “location”
10(d) “With regard to data governance, be consistent with open access to data, taking into consideration the principles of findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability (FAIR), of collective benefits, authority to control, responsibility and ethics (CARE) and of transparency, responsibility, user-focus, sustainability and technology (TRUST), as well as the recommendations set out in section III of the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization <i>Recommendation on Open Science</i> .”	Database managers	<p>“This database is consistent with internationally recognized open access data standards.”</p> <p>Optional language to consider and add, as appropriate, to the above statement:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “...including the FAIR principles” • “...including the CARE principles” • “...including the TRUST principles” • “...including the UNESCO <i>Recommendation on Open Science</i>” 	General disclaimer section
10(e) “Request that those submitting digital sequence information on genetic resources indicate that it is not subject to any restrictions that prohibit its sharing.”	Submitters	<p>“By submitting data to this database, you confirm that the data are not subject to any restrictions that would prevent their open sharing.”</p> <p>Data Submitter Agreement: “<input type="checkbox"/> I confirm that, to the best of my knowledge, the [genetic sequence] data here submitted are not subject to any restrictions that would prevent their open sharing through [database name]. Read more about the applicable national and international laws and rules governing access and benefit-sharing here: https://absch.cbd.int/”</p>	<p>Data Submission / Ethics</p> <p>Data Submission Portal (checkbox at upload stage or similar)</p>

⁶Submitters should be encouraged to provide both the original sampling location (*in-situ*) and, if applicable, the location where the material was obtained (e.g. from an *ex-situ* source), if known, as both types of information are valuable for scientific and policy purposes. We recommend databases to enable users to indicate different levels of provenance information by providing:

- A mandatory field for the geographical location of *in-situ* collection of the genetic resource.
- Optional fields for additional provenance information (e.g., where the resource was obtained (*ex-situ*), cultivated, or sequenced).